

JUST ONE MORE: FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH ALCOHOL USE AND ABUSE IN A MUNICIPALITY IN PARAÍBA

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ABSTRACT

This research entitled "Just one more: factors associated with alcohol use and abuse in a municipality in Paraíba". resulted from activities carried out as part of the Institutional Scientific Initiation Program at the Federal University of Campina Grande. The aim of the study was to analyze the factors associated with alcohol use in the municipality of Patos-PB. The methodological instrument used was the AUDIT (Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test) questionnaire.

Keywords: Identification. Problems. Alcoholic beverage.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to the drunken monkey hypothesis, by eating sun-dried fruit, monkeys get "high". "The odors of ripening fruit would help primates find scarce calories in tropical rain forests, given that ethanol is a relatively light molecule and is moved rapidly by winds through vegetation" (Stephens, Dudley, 2004).

This happens because of a strong attraction to the smell and taste of alcohol conferring a selective advantage to our primate ancestors, helping them to locate nutritious fruit at the peak of ripeness. This evolutionary trait would have been perpetuated by our genes, since we have

several enzymes responsible for alcohol digestion which would have no function if man did not consume this substance.

In what refers to drug use as an element of society and culture, we can cite the counterculture movements of the 1960s that would use drugs to express resistance to conservatism, seeking new forms of consciousness and behavior. "Legalize it, don't criticize it (...) Doctors smoke it. Nurses smoke it. Judges smoke it. Even lawyers, too".

In Brazil, when the Portuguese arrived, they discovered the indigenous custom of producing and drinking a fermented drink made from manioc, called Cauim. It was used in rituals, festivals and within a specific cultural context. The Indians also used tobacco, which was unknown to the Portuguese and other Europeans (Aureliano; Machado, 2012).

According to Oliveira (2013), the Portuguese knew the wine and beer and, soon after, they would learn how to make the cachaça; something that was not difficult, because to make sugar from sugar cane, in the process of making the must (juice in fermentation process), they ended up discovering a molasses that they put in the trough for animals and slaves, called "cagaça", which later came to be cachaça, distilled in clay alembic and much later, of copper.

Drinking alcohol is rooted in Brazilian culture. The act of drinking is part of our life as social beings. It is acceptable to state, for example, that liquor is used at São João festival, wine at Christmas, beer at Carnival and so on, not that they are exclusive, but the most representative of each one of these celebrations. Cachaça is a strong drink and close to the population. It has low cost and with little money you can drink enough to disturb yourself and others around you. The social and individual form of drinking is what is at stake when we talk about alcohol consumption, since there is a wide social disposition to consume it in the form of the most diverse beverages - distilled or fermented, strong or weak (Fernandes, 2002).

His study aimed to identify the problems related to alcohol consumption among adults aged 18 to 50 years in the municipality of Patos-PB, between August 2021 and August 2022.

From an epistemological point of view, we avoided an approach to the topic of alcohol use and abuse as an autonomous agent, as if it were an animate being acting on its own. In the opposite direction, the research problem considered the problems related to alcohol use and abuse as a broad phenomenon culturally constructed and reconstructed.

2 AIM

The study aimed to identify the problems related to the use and abuse of alcoholic beverages in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly between August 2021 and

August 2022. The study was conducted with individuals aged between 18 and 50 years in the municipality of Patos-PB, Brazil.

To perform the diagnosis of problems related to the use and abuse of alcoholic beverages, we sought to identify the gender, age prevalence of users, analyze the frequency of consumption by day, week or month. Frequency of consuming six or more doses at once. Times during the past 12 months when you were unable to stop drinking, once you had started. Times during the past 12 months when, because of alcohol, you were unable to perform as expected. Times during the past 12 months when you needed to drink in the morning to feel well during the day, after drinking the day before. Times over the last 12 months when you felt guilty or remorseful after drinking. Times over the last 12 months when you were unable to remember what happened because of drinking. Whether you caused injury or harm to yourself or another person after drinking and whether a relative, friend, doctor or other health professional was concerned that you drank or suggested that you stop.

3 METHODS

Among the numerous research instruments to identify problems related to the use of alcohol and other drugs, we will highlight three that have been developed with the support of the World Health Organization. The first is the CAGE, which is the best known and easiest to use. The second instrument is the Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST). The third instrument we adopted to conduct the research was the AUDIT, which is more comprehensive for detecting different levels of problems associated with different patterns of alcohol use. The original version of the AUDIT was developed by Saunders, J. et al. (1993). The questionnaire was disseminated on social networks and applied to individuals between 18 and 50 years of age who agreed to participate in the survey using Google Forms.

According to the World Health Organization (2004), a drug is defined as: any substance that is capable of modifying the function of living organisms, resulting in physiological or behavioural changes. Those that modify the central nervous system activity, increasing it (stimulants), reducing it (depressants) or altering our perception (disruptors) are called psychoactive. Among the psychoactive drugs some are sought after ("tropism") for their pleasurable effects, which may lead to their abuse or dependence - these are called psychotropic drugs.

Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire made available on Google Forms, during the period from August 2021 to August 2022.

Initially, the research form was shared on social networks by the student and the supervisor. Each person who answered the questionnaire was asked to disclose its link. Therefore, a procedure of disclosure and chain sampling known as snowball sampling was adopted.

Snowball sampling uses these links between members of the population to obtain a sample from some individuals who are members of the population. The method works from the indication by some individual of the population, of others who are also part of it and so on successively, being characterized in a format similar to a snowball that accumulates snowflakes when rolling and becoming increasingly larger (Dewes, 2013).

The questionnaire was answered by 464 individuals and, subsequently, the data were submitted to analysis in order to assess the results.

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Below are illustrations of the strategy used to disseminate the survey questionnaire on social networks.

4 RESULTS

The first question on the questionnaire was, do you agree to participate? All who participated (464 or 100%) stated that they wished to participate in the survey.

IMAGE - 1 GOOGLE FORMS SCREEN

Source: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1ASIKp3AR4IoPdeJVsdUV2i-qi_smY4Xfcxo58dNuTZU/

DISCUSSION

GRAPH 1 – GENDER

Source: researcher data (2022).

Graph 1 provides some information on the profile of the research participants. The slice in blue reveals that 262 or 56.5% of the participants were female, in red, 201 or 43.3% of the participants claimed to be male and 1 individual or 0.2% preferred not to state their gender.

GRAPH 2 - AGE GROUP

Source: researcher data (2022).

The young adult age group of 18 to 25 years old accounted for 252 or 54.3% of the survey participants, the second age group that most responded to the questionnaire was 35 to 50 years old, which equated to 147 or 31% of the respondents and 25 to 36 years old, the third age group with 65 or 14% of the participants.

GRAPH 3 - FREQUENCY OF DRINKING ALCOHOLIC BEVERAGES

Source: researcher data (2022).

The frequency of individuals drinking alcohol is most significant at 195 or 42% of the total 464 respondents. Then, 90 or 20% of the individuals stated that from two to four times a month. Whereas, 90 or 20.3% denied using alcoholic beverage. 71 or 15.3% use between two and three times a week; finally, 9 or 1.9% assumed that they drink four or more times a week.

GRAPH 4 - DOSE CONSUMPTION

Source: researcher data (2022).

The highest consumption of doses¹¹, 116 or 31.3% is among those who take one or two doses on the occasions they drink. 74 or 19.9% stated that they take three or four doses on

¹¹ Equivalents: a can of beer or a glass of draft beer (350 ml) is equal to a “dose”. Cachaça, vodka, whisky or cognac: half an American glass (60 ml) is equal to one and a half shots. A 1 litre bottle is equal to 25 shots. Wine: a glass is equal to a “dose”, a bottle (750 ml) = 5 “doses”.

drinking occasions. Thirdly, 73 or 19.7% consume ten or more doses on the occasions they drink. 56 or 15.1% mentioned taking five or six doses on drinking occasions. 52, or 14% consume seven, eight or nine doses on drinking occasions.

GRAPH 5 - FREQUENCY OF TAKING "SIX OR MORE DOSES" AT ONE TIME

Source: researcher data (2022).

The number of individuals who never took six or more doses at once¹² was 112 or 30%. In contrast, 111 or 29.8% of the sample took six or more doses less than once a month. The third group, 73 or 19.6%, weekly less than once a month. Fourthly, the group who drank monthly less than once a month was 69 or 18.5%. The last group, 8 or 2.1% consumed six or more drinks at once every or almost every day.

GRAPH 6 - TIMES OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS WHEN UNABLE TO STOP DRINKING, ONCE HAVING STARTED

Source: researcher data (2022).

230 or 73.5% reported that they were never able to stop drinking, once they started, over the last 12 months 36 or 11.5% responded that less than once a month over the past 12 months

¹² If you mark never, less than once a month, monthly or weekly, go on to questions 11 and 12. Equivalents: a can of beer or a glass of draft (350 ml) is equal to one dose. Cachaça, vodka, whisky or cognac: half an American glass (60 ml) is equal to one and a half shots. A 1 litre bottle is equal to 25 "doses". Wine: a glass is equal to a "dose", a bottle (750 ml) = 5 "doses".

they were unable to stop drinking once they started. 22 or 7% reported that they were unable to stop drinking once a month once they started. 15 or 4.8% of participants said that every day or almost every day over the last 12 months, they were unable to stop drinking once they had started. 10 or 3.2% said that weekly over the last 12 months, they were unable to stop drinking once they had started.

GRAPH 7 - TIMES DURING THE LAST 12 MONTHS WHEN, BECAUSE OF ALCOHOL, YOU WERE UNABLE TO PERFORM AS EXPECTED

Source: researcher data (2022).

In relation to the question on how many times over the past 12 months, because of alcohol, they were unable to do as expected, 238 or 76.6% assured that they never. 47 or 15% of the participants said less than once a month. 15 or 4.8% reported that monthly. And lastly, 7 or 2.2% stated that over the past 12 months, because of alcohol, they were unable to do as expected.

GRAPH 8 - TIMES OVER THE LAST 12 MONTHS WHEN YOU NEEDED TO DRINK IN THE MORNING TO FEEL WELL THROUGHOUT THE DAY AFTER DRINKING THE PREVIOUS DAY

Source: researcher data (2022).

Asked how many times over the past 12 months they had to drink in the morning to feel well during the day after drinking the previous day, 289 or 92.3% said never. 11 or 3.6% said less than once a month. 8 or 2.6% claimed that weekly over the past 12 months, they needed to drink in the morning to feel well throughout the day. 2 or 0.6% mentioned that monthly over the past 12 months, they needed to drink in the morning to feel well throughout the day after drinking the previous day. Finally, 3 or 1% ensured that monthly over the past 12 months, they needed to drink in the morning to feel good throughout the day, after drinking the previous day.

GRAPH 9 - TIMES IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS WHEN YOU FELT GUILTY OR REMORSEFUL AFTER DRINKING

Source: researcher data (2022).

On how often over the past 12 months have you felt guilty or remorseful after drinking. 174 or 57.4% said never. 79 or 25.3% said that over the past 12 months, they felt guilty or remorseful after drinking. 27 or 8.7% stated that monthly. 13 or 4.2% assured that every day or almost every day they blamed themselves or felt remorse.

GRAPH 10 - TIMES IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS WHEN YOU WERE UNABLE TO REMEMBER WHAT HAPPENED BECAUSE OF DRINKING

Source: researcher data (2022).

Regarding the times over the past 12 months when they were unable to remember what happened due to drinking, 190 or 60.3%, ensured that they never. 86 or 27.3% claimed less than once a month. 23 or 7.3% revealed that monthly. 9 or 2.9 ratified that weekly. 7 or 2.2% mentioned that every day or almost every day.

GRAPH 11 - HAVE YOU CAUSED INJURY OR HARM TO YOURSELF OR ANOTHER PERSON AFTER DRINKING

Source: researcher data (2022).

On having caused injury or harm to themselves or another person after drinking, 339 or 74.7% ratified that they had never. 84 or 18.5% said yes, but not in the last 12 months. 31 or 6.8% answered yes, in the last 12 months.

GRAPH 12 - DID A RELATIVE, FRIEND, DOCTOR OR OTHER HEALTH PROFESSIONAL WORRY ABOUT YOUR DRINKING OR SUGGEST THAT YOU STOP

Source: researcher data (2022).

As for whether a relative, friend, doctor or other health professional had ever worried about their drinking or suggested that they stop, 361 or 79% answered no. 53 or 11.6% said yes, but not in the last twelve months. 43 or 9.4% said yes in the last twelve months.

FINAL REMARKS

By analyzing a phenomenon that has long been present in the reality of Brazilian cities and communities, this study contributed to the understanding, albeit partial, of a problem that is associated with disease, death, quality of life and risk as to the ability to work of people who abuse alcoholic beverages.

The research evidenced that studies are needed to deepen the knowledge on the use and abuse of alcoholic beverages in the municipality of Patos-PB. In summary, this means thinking about how scientific research can contribute to the understanding of this problem.

From the data evidenced in the survey, we can present some conclusions: the first is that it is correct to state that this is no longer an infrequent situation, i.e., the idea that people make social use of alcoholic beverages is mistaken.

The second refers to the consequences that alcoholic beverages had in the lives of those who participated in the survey. Problems within private relationships, but which generate a perception and consequences for collective life, since there is a significant number of individuals who admitted having been warned by relatives or health professionals.

There is a third question that is associated with a broader dimension of the study; it is about preventing the use and abuse of alcoholic beverages. The answers revealed that the topic can be thought of from a broad context, given the risks to the individuals' health.

The conquest towards the prevention of alcohol-related diseases goes through the university's involvement, contributing with research and extension work to reinforce the work of the public authorities.

Finally, we have the conviction that it is the obligation of the research activity to offer feedback to the community that participated in the study. For this reason, researchers must disseminate the results obtained in order to contribute to the transformation of the lives of people who use alcoholic beverages in a harmful way.

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